

Convent of Panagia Eleousa (Lykousada Monastery)

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Entry tags: Christian, Greece, Religious Group, Greek, Language, Religious Place

Sited below a late 13th to early 14th-century fortress, the convent of Panagia Eleousa (Merciful Virgin), otherwise known as the Lykousada monastery, was built by a Vlach sebastokratorissa, known to us only by her monastic name Hypomone, who married into the powerful family of Epirote rulers. The convent was situated at Loxada (medieval name Lykousada), a village neighboring Phanari (where the fortress is) in Thessaly. Loxada border also the Pindos mountain range, which was inhabited by many Vlachs. Hypomone's monastery does not survive, as it was burnt to the ground during the Ottoman occupation of the region, in 1611-12. However, we can reconstruct the wealth and importance of the monastery through surviving chrysobulls (imperial issued documents) that record the convent's properties, including metochia and monyndria, as well as paroikoi (peasants). The monastery is of significant importance as it is among the few known material evidence of the transhumant, nomadic group of Vlachs.

Date Range: 1280 CE - 1620 CE

Region: Loxada, Thessaly

Region tags: Europe, Southeastern Europe, Southern Europe, Greece, Eastern Mediterranean, Greece, Thessaly, Northern Greece, Central Greece

The village of Loxada, near Phanari, Karditsa in Thessaly, Greece.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Dimitrios Sofianos. “Τα Υπέρ Της Μονής Της Παναγίας Της Λυκουσάδας Του Φαναρίου Καρδίτσας, Παλαιά Βυζαντινά (ΙΓ’ Και ΙΔ’ αΙ.) Έγγραφα (Χρυσόβουλλα κ.α.)” In *Ανατυπώσεις Εκ Του ΝΒ’*, 2004-2006, Τόμου Της Επετηρίδος Της Εταιρίας Βυζαντινών Σπουδών, 479-528. Athens: Εταιρίας Βυζαντινών Σπουδών, 2006.
- Source 2: Bees, Nikos. “Αποσπάσματα Ενός Χρυσόβουλου Για Τη Μονή ‘Παναγία Ελεούσα’ Στη Λυκουσάδα - Λωξάδα Της Καρδίτσας.” *Θεσσαλικό Ημερολόγιο* 12 (1987): 3-7.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: Dimitrios Sofianos. “Τα Υπέρ Της Μονής Της Παναγίας Της Λυκουσάδας Του Φαναρίου Καρδίτσας, Παλαιά Βυζαντινά (ΙΓ’ Και ΙΔ’ αι.) Έγγραφα (Χρυσόβουλλα κ.α.)” In *Ανατυπώσεις Εκ Του ΝΒ’*, 2004-2006, Τόμου Της Επετηρίδος Της Εταιρίας Βυζαντινών Σπουδών, 479–528. Athens: Εταιρίας Βυζαντινών Σπουδών, 2006.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Other [specify]: The place does not survive anymore. It was located near an entry to the Pindos mountains

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Merciful Virgin

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Notes: The sebastokratorissa of Thessaly

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The sebastokratorissa of Thessaly

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: Monasticism during the time Hypomone's husband John I Doukas of Thessaly (sebastokrator) took the monastic vow

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Field doesn't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Field doesn't know

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: N/A

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Liturgy

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: As per the chrysobulls for the monastery, yes.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– No

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

- ↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
 - No
- ↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
 - No
- ↳ Function for water management:
 - I don't know
 - Notes: Water pipes have been found around the villages.
- ↳ Part of the transportation network:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: N/A

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Convent of Panagia Eleousa (Lykousada Monastery), Sofianos, Dimitris. "Τα υπέρ της μονής της παναγίας της λυκουσάδας του φαναρίου καρδίτσας, παλαιά βυζαντινά (ΙΓ' και Ιδ' αι.) έγγραφα (χρυσόβουλλα κ.α.)". Athens: Εταιρίας Βυζαντινών Σπουδών, 2006.

Reference: Convent of Panagia Eleousa (Lykousada Monastery), Bees, Niko. "Αποσπάσματα Ενός Χρυσόβουλου Για Τη Μονή 'παναγία Ελεούσα' Στη Λυκουσάδα - Λωξιάδα Της Καρδίτσας" 12 (1987).